

EBFMC25-OP-18 · Congenital Complete AV Block in Preterm Neonates: Two Cases Surviving with Multidisciplinary Management

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Congenital complete atrioventricular block (CCAVB) is a rare but potentially life-threatening condition frequently associated with maternal autoantibodies, particularly anti-SSA and anti-SSB. The management of CCAVB in premature neonates presents considerable challenges due to their physiological immaturity.

Case Presentation: This report details two cases of preterm infants diagnosed with CCAVB linked to maternal anti-SSA and anti-SSB antibodies, both of whom were successfully managed through a comprehensive, multidisciplinary approach in an intensive care setting.

Discussion: During follow-up, both patients demonstrated stable cardiac function without evidence of significant ventricular dilation. Critical to the favorable outcomes were early diagnosis, appropriate hemodynamic and respiratory support, and meticulously tailored nutritional strategies.

Conclusion: These cases emphasize the essential role of individualized, multidisciplinary management in optimizing outcomes for premature neonates with CCAVB.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Autoantibodies, congenital complete AV block, multidisciplinary management, preterm neonates

INTRODUCTION

Congenital complete atrioventricular block (CCAVB) represents a rare yet potentially fatal disturbance of cardiac conduction, defined by the complete absence of atrioventricular impulse transmission. It is most frequently attributed to the transplacental passage of maternal anti-SSA/Ro and anti-SSB/La autoantibodies, which mediate immune-mediated injury and subsequent fibrotic replacement of the fetal atrioventricular conduction tissue (Scott et al., 1983).

While CCAVB is often suspected antenatally in the context of persistent fetal bradycardia, a subset of cases may remain undiagnosed until the postnatal period. In preterm neonates, the condition is associated with considerable clinical complexity, as it frequently coexists with profound hemodynamic instability, respiratory insufficiency, nutritional intolerance, and heightened vulnerability to infectious morbidity (Inoue et al., 2005). Herein, we report two cases of premature infants diagnosed with CCAVB, with a focus on the critical importance of prompt recognition, individualized supportive interventions, and a coordinated multidisciplinary care strategy in improving neonatal outcomes. Patient approvals were obtained for the inclusion of clinical findings and relevant diagnostic images in these case reports.

CASE PRESENTATION

Case 1: A female infant was delivered by emergency cesarean section at 26 weeks of gestation due to placental abruption and fetal distress. Birth weight was 1040 g. At birth, her heart rate was 50–55 beats per minute. Initial electrocardiogram (ECG) showed second-degree AV block, which progressed to complete AV block within two hours postnatally (Figure 1). Echocardiography revealed normal cardiac structure. Maternal screening revealed positive anti-SSA and anti-SSB antibodies, although the mother was asymptomatic.

Figure 1

Initial electrocardiogram of Case 1 demonstrating complete atrioventricular (AV) block

Case 2: A male infant was born at 32 weeks of gestation with a birth weight of 1600 g. During prenatal monitoring, he was diagnosed with a 2:1 AV block, and intrauterine treatment with IVIG and corticosteroids was administered. Postnatal ECG confirmed complete AV block (Figure 2). Maternal antibody testing was positive for anti-SSA and anti-SSB, without clinical signs of autoimmune disease.

Figure 2

Initial electrocardiogram of Case 2 demonstrating complete atrioventricular (AV) block

Postnatal Management

Both infants were admitted to the neonatal intensive care unit and managed through a multidisciplinary approach:

- Cardiac support: Intermittent epinephrine infusion and milrinone were administered to maintain heart rate and cardiac output. Serial echocardiography was performed to monitor left ventricular function.
- Respiratory support: Non-invasive ventilation with nasal CPAP was initiated, and surfactant therapy was provided to the first infant for respiratory distress syndrome.
- Nutritional support: Early parenteral nutrition followed by gradual transition to enteral feeding was implemented, with careful monitoring to prevent gastroesophageal reflux and aspiration.
- Infection control: Strict aseptic techniques and routine laboratory monitoring were applied.

Both infants achieved weight gain exceeding 3 kg, maintained stable cardiac function, and showed no progression of left heart dilation during follow-up. Decisions regarding permanent pacemaker implantation remain under ongoing evaluation.

DISCUSSION

Congenital complete atrioventricular block (CCAVB) is a rare but potentially life-threatening cardiac conduction disorder, most commonly resulting from the transplacental passage of maternal autoantibodies that mediate immune injury to the fetal atrioventricular node (Scott et al., 1983). In many cases, particularly when maternal autoimmune disease is subclinical or undiagnosed, the condition may remain unrecognized during gestation, with diagnosis first considered upon identification of fetal bradycardia or postnatal arrhythmias.

The presence of prematurity further complicates the clinical course of CCAVB, as the limited physiologic reserve and immaturity of vital organ systems render these infants particularly susceptible to hemodynamic compromise, respiratory insufficiency, and metabolic instability (Inoue et al., 2005). As such, optimal management requires a coordinated, multidisciplinary approach involving neonatology, pediatric cardiology, and nutritional support services.

The cases described herein demonstrate that, with rigorous echocardiographic surveillance, individualized hemodynamic management, judicious respiratory support, and carefully structured nutritional plans, favorable outcomes are attainable even in extremely preterm neonates with CCAVB. Despite the severity of prematurity, neither patient exhibited significant ventricular dysfunction during the course of follow-up.

Successful stabilization through supportive measures may defer or, in select cases, obviate the need for early permanent pacemaker implantation, thereby allowing for procedural intervention at a more clinically advantageous time point. According to the 2021 PACES expert consensus, indications for pacemaker implantation in pediatric patients include symptomatic bradycardia, a ventricular rate ≤ 50 bpm, left ventricular dysfunction, or ventricular dilation (Shah et al., 2021). Temporary pacing may be used to bridge critically ill premature infants until they reach appropriate weight and clinical stability. Reports in the

literature have documented successful permanent pacemaker implantation even in neonates weighing as little as 1.3 kg (Chimoriya et al., 2021; von Schnakenburg et al., 2002), demonstrating that low birth weight is not an absolute contraindication but requires experienced centers and careful timing.

Premature neonates with congenital complete atrioventricular block (CCAVB) present substantial clinical challenges, requiring early and precise diagnosis, intensive multidisciplinary management, and individualized long-term follow-up. With prompt identification and a comprehensive, coordinated approach to care, significant improvements in both survival and long-term quality of life can be achieved in these high-risk infants.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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